

W. Montgomery Watt's Approach to the Quran: An analysis

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 29, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Watt, Qur'ān, Analysis, Compilation</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5809312</p>	<p><i>Western Scholars have been writing on Islam, Quran and Holy Prophet for many centuries but Islam and the Quran have been the most misunderstood ones in the Western intellectual spear. Watt is included in the list of such Western Scholars who have studied the Holy Quran with historical criticism. In this study, the approach of W. Montgomery Watt (d. 2006) towards Quran is discussed from the perspective of method and mentality analysis. This paper evaluates some of his views about the Quran in this context, while examining the meaning of the word Quran, the textualization process of the Quran, the possibility of the chronological arrangement of the verses, the stylistic features of the Quran and the nature of revelation, it is determined that he has made a 'historical text' analysis. It is also determined that Watt has a 'dialogue-centered' vision as he emphasizes the Muslim-Christian dialogue in his works, and this situation affects both the style and methods he applied in his writings.</i></p>

Introduction

Scottish researcher W. Montgomery Watt, born in 1909, devoted more than half of his nearly a century of life to Islamic studies. He spent his childhood and youth with church activities, and for a while later at the University of Edinburgh. He has held positions such as Arabic lecturer, chair of Arab and Islamic Studies, visiting professor at Toronto and Georgetown universities, and president of the British Orientalists Association. Watt died in Edinburgh in 2006. He authored works in various fields such as the Quran, the history of Islamic sects, Islamic history, Sufism, Islam and Christianity.

It should be noted that historical-critical methods were effective in 20th century scripture research. The interest that emerged in the form of a return to the sources of classical antiquity especially with the Renaissance period turned towards the Biblical texts in the following period. With this method it was aimed to reach the most authentic forms of scriptures and to interpret the written evidences in the text (textual criticism), to determine the sources of the text (source criticism), to examine the verbal address forms before texting (form criticism) and to investigate the textualization process (redaction criticism). So these methods employed in the analysis of texts were also carried to 20th century Qur'anic studies.¹ These researchers with these methods approached the scriptures on the basis of elements such as neutrality, objectivity and anti-supernaturalism. This situation caused the related methods to experience "tensions" by their nature with traditional religious conceptions such as revelation, miracle, angel, and foretelling from the future.

The first assumption of the article is based on the aforementioned determinations that Watt analyzes the text of the Qur'an on the basis of historical-critical methods that were at the forefront of 20th century Western studies. In order to make this determination, the researcher's approach to the Quran will be subjected to a method analysis in the axis of historical-critical methods. The second assumption of this article is that Watt must have had difficulties in freely applying his method to the text of the Qur'an, due to his 'dialogue' understanding. Because, as mentioned briefly, historical-critical methods have a content that is at odds with theological and supernatural assumptions and analyze the sacred texts like any text. This study will try to reveal, within the framework of a mentality analysis, that the anxiety of "dialogue" with Muslims in mental background does not allow Watt to easily apply the method used in the text of the Quran.

The article includes the aforementioned determinations such as his evaluations on the word 'Quran', 'the process of compiling Quran', 'the chronological arrangement of the verses', 'the stylistic features of the Quran', 'the quality of revelation' and 'dialogue'.

Watt's Assessment of the Word Quran

Watt states that the words *karāe* and *Qur'an* are religious words that entered Arabia through Christianity. According to him, the verb *karāe* means 'to read' or 'to recite the sacred texts with awe' (to recite solemnly), while the *Quran* is derived from the Syriac *keryana*, meaning 'reading' or 'holy book lesson.' Although the word *Quran* means to read according to Watt, this meaning was acquired only in the later stages of

revelation, and in the early periods this word was more rather it means 'to recite'. As a matter of fact, the process of writing down the verses in the Mecca society, where oral culture is dominant, must have been recorded through written elements that serve as a reminder. It is most likely that the 'scripture text' is derived from *surta* meaning 'scriptures'.ⁱⁱ

Watt shares that in the later periods of the revelations, the aim of Muhammad evolved towards writing books rather than announcing the revelation to people. He opines that when the Quran is looked at chronologically, the word Book instead of the Quran started to be used more frequently over time. In addition, according to Watt, expressions such as bring a similar, or bring ten surahs, which are expressed as a challenge to the unbelievers in the Quran indicate that surah forms began to form in the period of Muhammad.

Here, a contradiction arises between Watt's etymological evaluations of the word surah and his conviction that writing may have had the most evocative function in the Mecca period, but that written records may have started in Medina. Namely, the meanings of the word surah (writing, scripture text, scriptures), which he attributes to Syriac origin, refer to a 'written' form. However, the expressions of bringing to a similar surah or bringing to ten suras are also mentioned in the Meccan suras. As such, it is concluded that 'written' surah forms began to form in the Meccan period. Looking at Watt's evaluations in the context of the subject as a whole, we are of the opinion that the contradictions between statements can be overcome by concluding that he is in the following opinion that in response to Gabriel's order to "read" him in the famous hadith, the expression of the Prophet *mâ aqrau* contains the meanings of both I cannot read or what to read and the second meaning seems more reasonable here. In addition, he stated that there are different versions of the hadith referring to the narration of Zühri. Watt does not claim that Muhammad was looking for a "source" for the Quran, based on his claim that he could read. He thinks that it is probable that Muhammad was as literate as the average Meccan merchant, he neither read the Bible nor was read to him.ⁱⁱⁱ

Considering Watt's evaluations regarding the word Quran, it can be seen that he continues the line of Richard Bell.^{iv} On the other hand, it should be noted that such determinations about the origin of the word Quran were made by other names including Bell, Arthur Jeffery, Noldeke, and in more recent studies, there are evaluations or references to the possible origins of the word Quran in Syriac or Hebrew. Watt's determinations at this point consist of sharing the ongoing etymological analyzes in Western literature.

Watt argues that the Prophet could read and write. According to him, the word *ummi* is derived from the Hebrew rather than "illiterate". In this context, it is possible to translate this word as "native" due to its usage in Arabic. Therefore, the word *ummi* has been misinterpreted by Muslims according to Watt

Views about compilation of the Quran

Watt does not make a definite choice as to whether it was written in the period of Muhammad (PBUH). According to him, when historical data is examined, it is possible that in a society where oral culture is dominant, the revelations of the Qur'an may be kept in memories for years. It was also written down in a certain form during the time of Muhammad. Watt argues that writing was known in Arabia at that time. Since it is known that Mecca is a commercial city, writing must have entered there as well. He argues that some verses of the Quran say that "accounts are written, angels write down the deeds of people, everything is recorded in a book, debts should be recorded in writing" etc, so these trade related descriptions also strengthen this assumption. Watt thinks that it is possible that some of the revelations were kept in memory in the period of Muhammad, but they were written down in the Mecca period. However, he thinks that there might be an increase in the material of revelation that was written down during the Medinan period.

After all, according to Watt, although Muhammad took the initiative to memorize revelations and bring them together in certain surah forms, yet after his death, it does not seem possible to determine clearly in the light of historical data the points such as how much of the revelations were included in the existing written material and in what form they were written. Watt, in addition states that some difficulties may have been experienced during the collection of revelations due to its suitable structure. According to him, the errors encountered in book printing despite modern technological developments confirm this point. Despite this, according to Watt, there is no possible change in the Quran.

Regarding the famous narration that mentions that a compilation was made in the time of the Prophet Abu Bakr, Watt writes that this narration is probably not valid. He approaches the narration at a distance and reveals some reservations in this context. According to him, the claim that the revelations mentioned in the narration were written on materials such as the shoulder blades of animals and palm leaves does not seem reasonable. He writes that although such materials have been used from time to time, there is no reason why papyrus should not have been used in Mecca. He further mentions that this claim implies that in the time of Muhammad, revelations were kept in circulating materials in a completely disorganized state, which is not possible according to Watt.

Watt, taking into account the dilemmas of the narration that the Quran was fully assembled during the period of Abu Bakr, concludes that the process of bringing the Quran together was not carried out during

the first caliph period. According to him, the narration of the collection of the Quran attributed to the period of Abu Bakr is likely that it was later invented by those who did not like Usman.

Watt, also critically analyzes the narration regarding the confiscation of the Quran during the time of Usman. According to him, one of the problems is that there are differences in the function of the copy, which is said to be with Hafsa in the narrations. He writes if Hafsa had a copy, it cannot be attributed to an official identity, and it cannot be said that it was the main source of reference in the period of Usman.

Watt in the final analysis states that there were some obscurity regarding the situation of the Quran in the period before Muhammad's death. He states that he firmly believes that the Quran collected during the time of Usman is the Quran in circulation today. According to him, what should be included in the text and what should be removed from the text, the number of surahs, the arrangement and the skeleton of the text were decided by the commission in the Ottoman period, and it should be acknowledged that the commission did an excellent job.

The point that should not be overlooked in Watt's evaluations in the context of the subject is that he refrained from presenting clear and precise sentences in the context of the 'authenticity' of the pre-Ottoman text. While making a 'historical-critical' determination he concludes that the text may have undergone revisions before it took its final form, Watt, on the other hand, does not give up his effort to present this situation in a manner that can be considered reasonable by Muslims.

Views about Chronological Organization of the Quran

The main sciences used to determine the chronology of verses in the tafsir literature are *asbāb al-nuzūl*, *Makkī - Madanī* and *al-nāsikh wal-mansūkh*. Watt states that the efforts of Muslims towards the chronological ordering of the verses in the light of the aforementioned sciences cannot be deemed worthless and that no new study on this subject can be deprived of these data.

As for the Western chronology searches, after the second half of the 19th century, a serious literature on the chronology of the Qur'an emerged in the following period, especially in the study of Nöldeke on the history of the Quran. Watt states that contemporary period chronology searches are based on historical and literary criticism methods. In the studies put forward in this context the data of commentary and seerah literature along with the stylistic features of the Qur'an are also used to determine the chronology. W. Muir, T. Noldeke, J.M Rodwell, H. Hirschfeld and R. Bell are among those researchers who employed the stylistic features of the Qur'an in their chronological order.

Watt examines Nöldeke's chronology proposals who divides the Meccan surahs into three periods and considers the Median surahs as one period. According to Noldeke, the first Meccan surahs are generally short. In these surahs, the verses are also short and have a rhythmic language and plenty of symbols. Passages usually begin with groups of oaths. The second period covers a transition period from the enthusiasm of the first period to the simplicity of the third period. Basic teachings are supported by examples from nature and history. As for the third Meccan surahs period, here we observe an increase in the frequency of the stories of the prophets with small differences in the content. There are significant differences in the context of the subject in the Median surahs. He opines that verses that include social arrangements and directly address people become more intense.

Watt claims that style is overemphasized in Nöldeke's criteria for chronology and criticizes this situation. According to him, although it is possible for certain stylistic changes to occur in certain periods, yet it is not correct to assume that the change continues in one direction and there is no fluctuation in style. He mentions that the name Rahman was used as a proper name in certain periods is also controversial. The main weakness of the Noldeke chronology is that it often treats the suras as unities. He points out that Noldeke rarely accepts that passages belonging to different histories are in the same surah. Watt acknowledges the difficulty of determining the chronological order of the passages from different periods in the surahs, although Watt criticizes Nöldeke's acceptance of the surahs as a whole.

Based on the chronology suggestions of Noldeke and Bell, Watt tries to determine the characteristics of the first Meccan suras. According to him in the first period passages before the emergence of an opposition against Muhammad topics such as Allah's power, God's sovereignty on the day of account, Heaven and Hell are prepared for the good and the wicked, and the thesis that man should realize his weakness and serve Allah are emphasized.

He writes that with the emergence of opposition, changes occur in expressions towards unbelievers and sinners. In this period; angels are mentioned for the first time in relation to the accounting day. He mentions that terms such as repentance, forgiveness and penance are also encountered in this period. He is of the view that Quranic verses mentioning Abraham as a prophet, verses mentioning his relationship with Ishmael, phrases of hanif, verses mentioning war, verses that order obedience to the prophet, Allah and His Messenger, disgrace and disgrace in this world, etc, belong to the Median period.

As a result, it is seen that Watt employs the sources of Quranic commentary, Hadith and sirah literature in his evaluations of possible chronology searches. It can also be determined that he makes use of historical-critical methods and tries to strengthen his findings by criticizing historical data. In addition, it is

seen that his search for chronology is based on the views of Richard Bell (d.1952) and Theodor Noldeke (d.1930), although he was critical about the Noldeke views.

It should be underlined that, in addition to historical data, Watt also traced the stylistic features parallel to the historical process in his search for chronology. Watt, who is seen to consider the stylistic features criterion of the text of the Qur'an, which is an important element in the search for chronology for his predecessors, as well as sharing his findings in the context of the subject, shows that in order to determine the chronological order of the Quran, literary elements are also used as well as historical elements in place.

Views about the Style of the Quran

The structure of the text of the Qur'an in the Western literature is among the important topics of the Qur'anic studies, especially in recent periods, and in this context, the "literary structures" of the Quran are analyzed. The acceleration of research on the text integrity of the Quran plays a role in the formation of such a research area.

In this context, Watt also analyzes the stylistic features of the Quran. In this context, he states that there is a different structure from Arabic poetry in the Qur'an and emphasizes the examples from various verses of both periods. Watt argues that it is possible to determine the passage units of the surahs based on the rhymes at the end of the verses, which is an important step in understanding the text correctly, given the fragmented structure of the Quran. According to Watt passages that have at least the same rhyme can be analyzed by taking it as a whole.

Watt presents examples from the Quran about the ways in which various didactic forms of expression are used. However, he adds that these uses are far from providing definite information about the revelation of the verses. Evaluating the rejection of this accusation by the Qur'an, which is described as the word of the priest by its contemporaries due to its stylistic features, Watt admits that a large part of the Quran does not resemble the words of the priest. On the other hand, Watt refers to the existence of a deep-rooted tradition among the *Sámi* peoples of conveying a supernatural knowledge through unusual verbal forms such as rhyme and tries to make sense of the accusations the Quran is exposed to. Watt speaking of passages beginning with vows admits that these patterns have an impressive stylistic feature. He opines that the vows diminish in the later stages of revelation.

According to Watt, the purpose of living depictions of heaven and hell is to make an impact on the conscience of the addressees. In his opinion in these scenes, difficulties arise from the verbal address forms that the text contains from time to time. The disconnections in the plot and the sudden change of the addressee are just a few of them. Still, Watt argues that such verses do not lose anything in their fascination. Expressing that stories and parables are also used in the context of people's exemplary or exemplary practices, Watt points out to the Surah Yusuf as an example that shows that a section of the main message is included in such narratives from time to time, and then the narrative continues from where it left.

A significant amount of metaphors and similes are present in the Quran. The accusation of people as 'deaf', 'mute' and 'blind' for closing their eyes to the truth, and the sealing of hearts refers to the explanation of a normally spiritual situation with material elements. Watt emphasizes the employment of commercial words in a religious context.

Regarding his evaluations on the language of the Qur'an, Watt states that the claim that the language of the Qur'an is entirely Arabic and that all words have Arabic origin in Islamic literature arises from a theological concern. According to him, the Quran introducing itself as "an Arabic address" does not require that all of its words be of Arabic origin. Underlining that it is quite natural that words from different languages have entered the languages of Arabs who are engaged in trade, Watt draws attention to Arthur Jeffery's work which deals with the issue of words included in the Quran from other languages.

The connection that Watt established between style changes and 'revision' while evaluating the stylistic features of the Quran is also noteworthy.

According to Watt, some points such as the inclusion of a different topic in a homogeneous passage, sudden changes in the length of the verses, juxtaposition of passages belonging to different dates are the evidences of revision in the text. Watt, who also exemplifies matters such as revelations and the explanation of ambiguous words, tries to 'justify' the issue for Muslims by establishing a connection between what he calls revision and the 'abrogation' in the tafsir literature.^{vi} According to Watt, during the last compilation of the Quran, it was wished to include a small unit in the original text but he states that in the final analysis this may not have been done.

Views about Revelation

Various hypotheses have been put forward by Western non-Muslim researchers in the context of the sources of the Quran. The study of the sacred texts in contemporary Western literature with a 'secular' perspective seems to have been effective in entering into a secular quest for the source of the Quran

Watt states that the use of the word revelation in the Qur'an can be understood as 'some quick suggestion' or 'a statement of thought through inspiration'. It should be remembered that he also uses the term revelation in one of his works where he prefers the term revelation in all subtitles related to revelation.

Indeed, the issue of what meanings these concepts have in which religion is important. He interpreted revelation in these words:

It can be said that the Quran reveals all the basic truths of the Abrahamic religion, which was adopted by Jews and Christians in its own style. I think the only logical explanation for this is that Muhammad was inspired by God like the Old Testament prophets.

In providing a 'modern' account of Muhammad's experience of revelation Watt introduces Carl Gustav Jung's (d. 1961) concept of the collective unconscious. Accordingly, God is based on the subconscious experience of man and the person feels God as a psychological reality. Watt thinks that Muhammad is sincere in his claim that he received revelation. According to him, these words come to Muhammad from his subconscious. At this point, it seems possible to see the 'revelations' of Judaism, Christianity and Islam as 'contents' derived from the experience which Jung defined as the collective subconscious. In this context, Watt argues that the revelations communicated to Muhammad came to him through his subconscious.

Watt ultimately admits that Jung's attempts to provide a modern explanation for revelation from the collective unconscious concept cannot be seen as a final form of explanation. However, he argues that the nature of revelation that can be discussed in this context is an issue that should not be denied.

After having a look at the content of the discussions about the source or sources of the Quran in the Western literature, it is seen that some of them are extremely pejorative and contain claims that lack academic value. Watt's approach to the source of the "revelation" of the Qur'an, in a more modern and 'reconciling' method and an academic style, can be seen as an important feature that distinguishes him from others at this point.

Dialogue

W. Montgomery Watt makes room for the talk of 'dialogue' in a significant part of his works on various fields. Terms such as 'religious pluralism' or 'interfaith dialogue' have been accepted as an important agenda item in the literature written with a Christian point of view, especially for the last half century, and remarkable studies are encountered in this context. These terms contain the idea that world religions essentially contain the same message in essence, in this context; one religion should neither be 'exclusivist' nor 'inclusivist' on the other. It would be appropriate to read the title with the following quote from Watt:

There is no problem predicting that religions will enter any mix in the future; as long as the various religions of the world have each other, the mountain covered with clouds on which God sits invisible. While accepting as the same climbers, the first step is to get to know each other mutually.

It is clear in his work that Watt pays special attention to the idea of 'dialogue'. He points out this idea in one of his other book in these words:

One of the characteristics of the second half of the twentieth century is the increase in the relationship between followers of different religions. As a result, a Western researcher no longer has the right to judge Asian religions as he did in the 19th century ... The term 'dialogue' is used for this new relationship between different religions. Despite the ambiguity of the term, when it comes to the Qur'an, this term refers to seeing the Qur'an as a holy book and to display a respectful attitude towards it and its believers, even if that belief is not shared.

From these statements of Watt, it can be easily noticed that the idea of "dialogue" is behind his recommendation to pay attention to Muslims and Muslims' Holy Book. However the issue is not only a suggestion of style, but also has a nature that affects the way of reading the Quran. For example, when looking at Watt's thoughts on the nature of revelation, it is seen that Islam tries to present the concept of revelation in a way that can be reconciled with the concept of inspiration of other religions. It should be noted that Watt introduced a definition to the term revelation, 'in spite of the Quran and Muslims', and suggested that Muslims should also 'accept' the phenomenon of revelation, which he tried to make understandable based on Jung. Perhaps it would be appropriate to re-read his thoughts on other issues in this context. It would be unfair to claim that Watt's analysis of the Quran and revelation is entirely far from academic. In his analysis of the Qur'an, he writes:

In the last quarter of the century, the increasing relations between Muslims and Christians made it necessary for the Christian scholar to present his views in a form that was acceptable to the dozens of them, rather than arbitrarily attacking Muslim readers. The necessity of courtesy and looking from above it requires us not to mention

it as the work of the mind of Muhammad... That is why I have altered or destroyed all the expressions that imply that Muhammad was the author of the Quran (including those that speak of his 'sources' or 'influences' on it).

It is noteworthy that Watt's concern for dialogue goes beyond his empathetic style and influences his method as well. For example, the verb 'produce' used to express the phenomenon of revelation in Bell's Introduction to the Qur'an was replaced by 'reveal' by Watt in Bell's Introduction to the Qur'an.

Watt's statement that the situation of Christians is very different reveals his emphasis on the 'historicity' of the verses. However, his exemplification of the historicity of the verses in the context of the relationship between Muslim and Christian clearly summarizes the theological framework affecting his method.

The fact that the concern behind Watt's such interventions is 'Muslim-Christian dialogue' is expressed in his sentences:

In theological disputes between Christianity and Islam, it has been tried to remain neutral. For example, to avoid deciding whether the Quran is the word of God, I avoided using the expressions 'says God' or 'says Muhammad' when referring to the Qur'an and said only 'says the Koran'

Conclusion

Watt examines the Quran in a 'history-centered' context on the basis of historical-critical methods, analyzing the text from its own history. It has been determined that he abandoned the classical orientalist style towards Muhammad, emphasized that non-Muslims should refrain from a language that hurt Muslims in their Qur'anic studies, and he paid maximum attention to this issue. He does not mention the "author" or "external sources" of the Quran. It has been noticed that the claims of historical-critical methods such as objectivity and scientificity contributed to Watt's adoption of an understanding and academic style; however, it has been clarified that the concern of 'dialogue' constitutes the most important element in the sensitivity of style. It has been determined that Watt's having a 'dialogue' centered vision affects not only his style but also the method he applied and the results he reached. It has been determined that the thesis that the revelations might have been subjected to some additions and deletions during the period of Muhammad was put forward in a manner expected to be accepted by Muslims, with emphasis such as the theory of abrogation of the Quran and its adoption of a gradual method, rather than a secular perspective. Based on all of these determinations, the fact that ideological or theological concerns can disrupt an academic activity to a certain extent is embodied in Watt example. In the final analysis; the approaches towards the Quran in the Western literature maintain their diversity and dynamism today. It is certain that recent Western studies deserve more attention, when Qur'anic studies have become a separate field and Muslim researchers have become an active subject of the field.

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